

Critical overview of Forex VPS

Research paper by

Monica Alexis

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What is a forex vps?

Forex Virtual Private Server (a.k.a [Forex VPS](#)) allows currency trader to improve Algorithmic trading results and run automated expert advisors (EA), non-stop 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. It doesn't matter what software trading platform you are using. Original currency exchange servers are compatible with all known automated software platforms — cTrader, AlgoTrader, MetaTrader, JForex, NinjaTrader, TradeStation, MultiCharts and other.

How to Use a Forex VPS?

These are specially optimized remote servers which are used to host forex trading software, expert advisors and indicators in order to allow for continuous, round-the-clock trading even when the trader's local computer is not running. A forex VPS requires physical servers to be placed in specially constructed data centers with controlled environments for optimal performance. The optimizations begin with the use of special ultra-fast hardware and end with the use of unique software technologies as [AlwaysUP® Protection](#). That service guaranteed execution of currency trades with minimal latency and time slippage.

How Does a ForexVPS Work?

True story of authentic services.

The real, original service developed by NextPointHost.com, before more than decade is always on-line. It won't reboot during the currency trading week. It not affected by the power outages or internet connection interruptions. You don't need to worry about keeping your PC permanently on-line. All this is accomplished with the use of complicated high availability virtualization technologies that manage the partitioning (virtualization), of physical hosts into smaller sub-units. Each sub-unit runs its own isolated operating system (OS). The OS is identical with the OS of standard PC. This eliminates the need to learn new management skills. You can migrate your automated trading processes right on their platform for increased profit.

Cross-Connection (X-connect).

NextPointHost X-connect guarantees a fast order execution which means it will drastically improve the chances your trades to be executed by broker's servers in front of other traders who are competing for the same price. This means that you'll have a strong competitive advantage before all other participants in the forex market, who have slower connections and higher latency. They will learn about fluctuation in the market seconds after you. Until they react, your order will be already executed. If you are serious about making money with forex, strongly recommend you to choose this option.

Advantages of Cross Connection.

- Very fast order processing due to lower latency.
- Reduce Slippage. The NextPointHost's cross-connection ForexVPS servers have 10 000 times lower latency compared to 3/4G GSM Networks.
- Perfect for high-frequency trading systems.
- Improve trading and that's lead to better profit.
- Access from any device with Internet.
- 99.9999% Uptime Guarantee.
- AlwaysUP Protection® - unique technologies guaranteeing the stable work of our servers in all possible situations.
- 24/7 Support.

How X-connect achieves ultra-low latency?

NextPointHost's network administrators control and use a broad range of network assets. X-connect is used to increase performance, decrease latency (the time it takes to transmit information), and improve traffic flow management. Cross-connection can provide a more consistent and reliable experience than Internet-based links. They are also a valuable resource for minimizing data loss and promoting disaster recovery when emergencies happen. Simply put, X-connect are physical cables that make direct links between the broker's servers and your forex server. In this case, the traffic goes through a single cable without having to be directed from one network to another till it reaches its destination. This guarantees ultra-fast speed, network reliability, and low latency.

Why NextPointHost Cross Connection can impact your trading success?

Are you trading at forex market using expert advisor (EA) or robot or any other tool for Algorithmic trading? If so reading up, next lines. Do you know that probably not earning as much as maximum possible. Your winning strategy losing some amount of money, due to network latency. Your trading edge depends on it. Pay attention! Think about this.

- Where are you located in the world?
- Then where are your broker's servers?

How farther you are, the longer it takes of broker to receive your orders. Why this is important? Well - imagine that you are wanting to buy or sell at a specific price. Just because you see it on your screen, doesn't mean you'll get that price. This is because forex prices are always moving. It takes time for the broker to receive your trade. The

difference between the price you're after and the price your broker filled you, can cost you big time. This is the biggest mistake retail traders make! We're talking about hundreds if not thousands of dollars. What if you can be right next to the broker? The same data center. That's exactly **what “NextPointHost” do** with their cross-connection forex servers!

- They are hosting the servers of many major brokers!
- Your broker use their first-class high availability infrastructure.
- They're knowing what you need!
- They guarantee your link to the broker 24/7.
- They are executing trades 10000 times faster than your 4G mobile network.
- This is 250 times faster as you can blink

Stop risking! Invest in the right tools, you need! Try their cross-connection today. Visit their live chat to learn more.

How to Recognize the Original Forex VPS?

The Forex VPS service has been created by <https://NextPointHost.com/forex-vps> before more than a decade! This is the only real provider, who offers reliable servers for auto trading. Taking advantage of the incredible success of this service, many fraudsters posted offers about it. Go through these telltale signs that

can help you identify an original Forex VPS from a counterfeit, and make sure you are not a victim of scammers.

Usage of tactics, that simulate urgency.

In marketing textbooks is written:

*“There is nothing that kills eCommerce conversion rates faster than customer hesitation. Anytime a customer thinks “maybe later”. He opens the window to a sale-killing distraction - an offer from a competitor, a phone notification, or even a change of heart rate. The only way to get shoppers to take buying action immediately is to **simulate urgency**.”*

I personally know more than 25 ways to create urgency without people to feel pushed off. I'll share you most commonly used tricks by Russian, Chinese, USA, and other international crooks.

Lie #1: Unreal limited-time discounts

An offer bound by time is a powerful method for creating urgency feeling. Time limitations trigger your desire to avoid losses especially if the offer seems too good, forcing you to act quicker than they might do it in a normal situation.

STOP! Take a deep breath! Use common sense! Continue exploring at a normal pace. I'm sure that you will find more traces of scam. Scammers are greedy. They usually use several tricks at once.

Lie #2: See what other customers are “buying” in real-time.

Most of the people follow what others are doing. The deceivers know that. They will show you what others are “buying” from them in real-time. In this way, they're providing social proof and increase the initially created fear of exhausting the product.

Remember it! All this information is fake. The biggest brands like **NextPointHost.com** - the creators of the “Forex VPS” service, have enough resources to constantly provision new servers. The business model of all real companies have a plan for growth. There is no

business manager who will let his company to stop selling well-sold item. In the worst case, if sales outstrip the company's production capacity, the managers will increase prices. This is the standard market rule. If there is high demand and low supply, prices go up.

Lie #3: Many positive reviews from happy customers.

Stay away from services that claim to have hundreds of positive reviews from satisfied customers. This is a sufficient condition to be sure that it is a fraud. We are individuals, different from each other. The requirements of people are different. It's not possible to create a product which suits perfectly the needs of all clients over the world, especially when we are talking for hundreds of sales. Even the bestsellers receive some amount of negative comments from haters. It

shouldn't be underestimated the fact, that satisfied customers usually don't write positive comments. Writing comments is a priority for unsatisfied customers.

Lie #4: Meet the amazing team

Meet our amazing **ForexVPS** Team

We're proud of what we do and we're here to help around the clock.

Name	Title	Quote
Duff Devaul	Server Engineer	"Hardware and software performance is crucial to successful forex trading, and I enjoy providing it. Trading is my favorite game."
Arturo Ferracuti	Head of Client Support	"I love surfing and spending my spare time at the beach with friends and family. I've been trading Forex since 2011."
Daniel Fukuda	Head of Development	"I'm coming from IT background but I've been involved with financial markets since early 2011 and exclusively Forex since 2013."
Dominic Gilbert	Associate Director	"I have over a decade of experience in Forex trading. VPS & algorithmic trading is something I live and breath."

Lie #4: Meet the amazing team

Doesn't it look weird to you, big company from which many people constantly "buy" services will have a team of only 9 persons? In addition, 4 people in this team are "director" and others are "customer representative". Where is the mid-level management, office assistants, interns, developers, etc? Have you seen it anywhere the amazing team of Facebook, Google, Microsoft, etc of the biggest brands? The biggest asset in every company are people. There is no businessman who wants to show his team publicly. Showing your team in public is like owning gold bars, then to "shouting come on over here. See how much gold is available here". If you are the owner of that "gold", would you do such a thing? I don't think.

Displaying the team is a way of distraction.

Fraudsters use it as a filler when they have nothing else to put on their pages. Real companies have a lot of business experience. They can write books about every aspect of service. That's why they don't need a filler. Remember it! Be careful when you see page where is promoted the team instead of product details.

Lie #5: Annoying, unwanted chat invitations.

This is another way of being pressured to buy the service quickly. These aren't real humans. These are automated chat robots (chatbots). Make Google search about "Watson Assistant" or "Chatbot" and will understand how powerful are these systems. They are pre-trained with content from a specific industry. Chatbots

understand your historical chat or call logs, searching for answers in knowledgebases, ask you about more clarifications, redirect you to humans who will continue the conversation, and even give you training recommendations to hone your conversational abilities.

Lie #6: Self-determination as a trusted provider.

International fraudsters want to win your trust. It's common practice to self-determination and highlight many times that the scam is "trusted"! Repeating the same word many times, makes your mind subconsciously believe in the scam. Believing in "Think Huge" Scam you give enough time of crooks to hide their tracks. You will give them enough time to drain your credit card and to disappear. Now is the time to wake up! Go away from this website. The "Think Huge" is a scam!

Similarity to the original Forex VPS service.

See original plan names!

The image shows a screenshot of a VPS service pricing page. On the left, there is a vertical navigation menu with three categories: 'Basic Plans' (orange), 'Advanced Plans' (blue), and 'PRO Plans' (blue). Three arrows point from these categories to the main content area. A green arrow points from 'Basic Plans' to the 'London Data Center' plan, labeled 'Original Plan-1'. A red arrow points from 'Advanced Plans' to the 'Frankfurt Data Center' plan, labeled 'Original Plan-2'. An orange arrow points from 'PRO Plans' to the 'Sofia Data Center' plan, labeled 'Original Plan-3'. The main content area displays three plan cards. Each card includes a data center name, a list of features, a 'SPECIAL PRICE' in EUR MONTHLY, and a 'GET STARTED' button. The London Data Center plan is priced at €26.25, the Frankfurt Data Center plan at €18.75, and the Sofia Data Center plan at €15. The background of the page features a hand holding a glowing blue sphere.

- **Basic**
- **Advanced**
- **PRO**

These are names of original service.

The plans names used by fake Russian-Chinese website.

* October VPS Promotion: Get up to 25% off new orders!

The screenshot shows a VPS pricing table with four columns: Basic, Basic+, Standard, and Professional. A red oval highlights the plan names and their corresponding icons. A large red watermark 'SCAM ACTS IN ACTION' is overlaid on the table. A chat window on the right shows a customer support agent named Alex.

	Basic Forex VPS	Basic+ Most Popular VPS	Standard Forex VPS	Professional Forex VPS
VPS RAM	1.5 GB (1536 MB)	2 GB (2048 MB)	3 GB (3072 MB)	4 GB (4096 MB)
VPS CPU (Cores)	1	1	2	4
VPS Disk Space (SSD)	40 GB	50 GB	60 GB	80 GB
VPS System (OS)	Windows Server 2008 Windows Server 2012 Windows Server 2016 Windows Server 2019	Windows Server 2008 Windows Server 2012 Windows Server 2016 Windows Server 2019	Windows Server 2008 Windows Server 2012 Windows Server 2016 Windows Server 2019	Windows Server 2008 Windows Server 2012 Windows Server 2016 Windows Server 2019
Dedicated IP Address		✓	✓	✓
Web Control Panel		✓	✓	✓
Locations	New York London Manchester Zurich	New York London Manchester Zurich Amsterdam Frankfurt Singapore Tokyo	New York London Manchester Zurich Amsterdam Frankfurt Singapore Tokyo	New York London Manchester Zurich Amsterdam Frankfurt Singapore Tokyo

Chat window: ForexVPS Sales
Alex (Customer support)
Alex: how can I help you?

Notification: Mantas from Chigwell, GB Recently bought Basic VPS 43 minutes ago (WHMCS Data)

The Russian-Chinese website uses almost the same names as the original. Of course, it ornaments these names with the methods for creating urgency feeling.

Replicas copy the original colors.

All the fake sites I've come across use copies of the original NextPointHost's green, orange and blue colors. The guys who "think huge" even copy the texts, images, video and created design with points. In this way, they create an impression in the visitor for similarity with the name of "next point".

Many fake websites with names containing ForexVPS.

As is often occurs the "robbers shout, keep the thief". I found more than 10 different websites controlled by "Think Huge" pyramid. Be careful! Common between all of them is the fact that in the domain name they contains "forexvps", "fxvm", "forexcheapvps", "fxvps", etc commonly used abbreviations of real "Forex VPS" service. That's why is possible search engines to show you fake website when want to find the website of the authentic service. Follow the advice, discussed earlier in this report in order to avoid low-quality fake products.

Conclusion

The original Forex VPS service is the perfect way for making automatic trading 24/7 without interruptions. This product increases algorithmic trading earnings with more 50% percent. The statement is based on statistics provided by NextPointHost.com. Don't forget the fact that currency exchange is business with high risk, where profit or loss depends on many other factors. As a consequence, the profit increase in your particular case may be at other levels. You must be very careful! Use only the original service! The market is flooded with fake "forex vps" services. The fake forex servers put the trading at serious risk. They are dangerous. Never use such cheap, low-quality Chinese products. Coming soon my new research paper for the misleadings created by web hosting companies. It will explain why you can not use Windows VPS servers as "Forex VPS".